

AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
BOOK STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)

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1. Introduction

1.1) Purpose

The Software is for Online Book Store.

It allows registered users to do the following:

- Login
- Browse based on price, title, and category
- Buy books

It allows registered admin to do the following:

- Add books
- Update books

1.2) Scope

It can be used in any company to provide online buying and selling of books.

1.3) Technologies used

This project will be a web based application to be developed in Eclipse indigo having

- Database Design (Oracle 10g)
- Form Design (java and html)
- Coding (jsp and servlets)

1.4) Overview

Online Book Store's main facilities available in this project are:-

- Maintaining book details.
- Purchase feature.
- Add and update book details

2. Overall Description

2.1) Goals of proposed system

2.1.1) Planned approach towards working

The working in the organization will be well planned and organized. The data will be stored properly in data stores, which will help in retrieval of information as well as its storage.

2.1.2) Accuracy

The level of accuracy in the proposed system will be higher. All operation would be done correctly and it ensures that whatever information is coming from the center is accurate.

2.1.3) Reliability

The reliability of the proposed system will be high due to the above stated reasons. The reason for the increased reliability of the system is that now there would be proper storage of information.

2.1.4) No Redundancy

In the proposed system utmost care would be that no information is repeated anywhere, in storage or otherwise. This would assure economic use of storage space and consistency in the data stored.

2.1.5) Immediate retrieval of information

The main objective of proposed system is to provide for a quick and efficient retrieval of information. Any type of information would be available whenever the user requires.

2.1.6) Immediate storage of information

In manual system there are many problems to store the largest amount of information.

2.1.7) Easy to Operate

The system should be easy to operate and should be such that it can be developed within a short period of time and fit in the limited budget of the user.

2.2) Background

Online book store is a web application to allow users to select books through internet and get them delivered to their doorsteps.

It allows registered users to do the following:

- Login
- Browse and query books based on price, title, and category
- Buy books

It allows registered admin to do the following:

- Add books
- Update books

For a bookstore to remain successful, it must improve “the experience of buying books,” says Alex Lifschutz, an architect whose London-based practice is designing the new Foyles. He suggests an array of approaches: “small, quiet spaces cocooned with books; larger spaces where one can dwell and read; other larger but still intimate spaces where one can hear talks from authors about books, literature, science, travel and cookery.” The atmosphere is vital, he adds. Exteriors must buzz with activity, entrances must be full of eye-catching presentations

2.3) User Characteristics

- Every user should be:
- Comfortable of working with computer.
- He must also have basic knowledge of English

2.4) Constraints

- GUI is only in English.
- Login and password is used for identification of user and there is no facility for guest.

2.5) Definitions of problems

Problems with conventional system are –

2.5.1) Manual system

The manual system of performing a task is often more complicated and time consuming whereas if the same system is automated the time factor and complications are reduced to a great extent.

2.5.2) Lack of immediate retrievals

The information is very difficult to retrieve and to find particular information Like – E.g.
- To find out about the different books by same author or other books in same category the user has to search a number of websites or bookstores .This results in inconvenience and wastage of time.

2.5.3) Price and selection

The major disadvantage of buying books through physical stores is that we cannot always have the complete range of books to select also the price of a book can vary from to shop.

2.5.4) Changing Retailers

Another disadvantage of physical bookstore is that it not always easy to switch suppliers and vendors.

2.6) Alternative Solutions

2.6.1) Improved Manual System

One of the alternative solutions is the improvement of the manual system.

Anything, which can be done by using automated methods, can be done manually. Automation reduces the manpower requirement of a particular company.

2.6.2) Better selection and Price guarantee

One advantage of shopping online is being able to quickly seek out deals for items or services provided by many different vendors. Shipping costs (if applicable) reduce the price advantage of online merchandise, though depending on the jurisdiction, a lack of sales tax may compensate for this.

2.6.3) Retailers

Advantage of online bookstore is that it is always easy to switch suppliers and vendors without changing the experience of customers.

3. Feasibility Study

The highlights of the feasibility analysis are:

3.1) Technical Feasibility

The Online Bookstore is feasible technically, although there is some risk. Online Bookstore risk regarding familiarity with Internet order applications is high.

- The Marketing Department has little experience with Internet-based marketing and sales.
- The IT Department has strong knowledge of the company's existing order systems; however, it has not worked with Web-enabled order systems.

- Hundreds of retailers that have Internet Order applications exist in the Market place Online Bookstore risk regarding familiarity with the technology is medium.
- The IT Department has relied on external consultants and an Internet Service Provider to develop its existing Web environment.
- The IT Department has gradually learned about Web systems by maintaining the current Web site.
- Development tools and products for commercial Web application development are available in the marketplace, although the IT department has little experience with them.
- Consultants are readily available to provide help in this area.

The project size is considered medium risk :-

- The project team likely will include less than 5 people.
- Business user involvement will be required.

The compatibility with Online Bookstore existing technical infrastructure should be good.

- The current Order System is a client-server system built using open standards.

An interface with the Web should be possible.

- Retail stores already place and maintain orders electronically.
- An Internet infrastructure already is in place at retail stores and at the corporate headquarters.

- The ISP should be able to scale their services to include a new Order System.

3.2) Economic Feasibility

A cost–benefit analysis was performed A conservative approach shows that the Internet Order System has a good chance of adding to the bottom line of the company significantly.

Intangible Costs and Benefits :-

- Improved customer satisfaction
- Greater brand recognition

3.3) Organizational Feasibility

From an organizational perspective, this project has low risk. The objective of the system, which is to increase sales, is aligned well with the senior Management’s goal of increasing sales for the company. The move to the Internet also aligns with Marketing’s goal to become savvier in Internet Marketing and sales. The users of the system, Internet consumers, are expected to appreciate the benefits of Online Bookstore Web presence. And, management in the retail stores should be willing to accept the system, given the possibility of increased sales at the store level.

4. Data Tables

4.1) Customers Table

All the details of valid customers i.e. people who have successfully registered to our website are stored here. It includes their username and password.

4.2) Books Table

All the details of the books in the store or warehouse are stored in these tables. It includes name, ID, category, quantity, publisher, image, price and description.

4.3) Contacts Table

This table includes the messages and the details of the contact person. It includes name, email, phone, company and message.

5. Snapshots

HOME

ABOUT US

MY ACCOUNT

REGISTER

BOOKS

CONTACT US

ADMIN

ADD BOOK

UPDATE

ORDER

MESSAGES

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar displaying 'localhost:8080/BookStore-22.7/Message1.jsp'. The page content includes a header with 'Book Store' and a navigation menu with 'Home', 'Add Book', 'Update', 'Messages', and 'Logout'. The main content area features a table with the following data:

Name	Email	Phone	Company	Message
Harsh	harsh@gmail.com	9876543321	CMC ltd	Hello!
Saksham Kakkur	saksham@gmail.com	8782174872	CMC private ltd	Hello!
Arshmeet	arsh.rekhi@yahoo.com	8134734981	TCS pvt ltd	Online book store.
gurpreet	gps@gmail.com	9654654616	cmc limited	i would like to meet you

The browser's taskbar at the bottom shows various application icons and system tray information, including the time '10:41' and date '27-09-2014'.

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